

BOOLEAN SPACE AND FAN-GOTTESMAN COMPACTIFICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

A Boolean space is a zero dimensional, compact and T_0 –topological space. Also, it is called Stone space. There are a lot of methods for obtaining compact space. Aleksandrov, Stone-Cech, Wallman and Fan-Gottesman compactification are four of them. In this paper, it is discussed Fan-Gottesman compactification of regular space with normal base and necessary and sufficient conditions for Fan-Gottesman compactification of T_3 space to be a Stone space are given by considering relation between the Stone space and compact space.

Keywords: Boolean space, Fan-Gottesman compactification

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